

The Current Situation of Ang Thong Province's Court Doll Distribution

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Abstract—This research is objected to study the pattern and channel of distribution of Ang Thong's court doll OTOP product and try to develop the quality of distribution of the court doll product. The population of this research is 50 court doll manufacturers of Ang Thong's court doll. The data and information was collected by using the questionnaire and use percentage, mean and standard deviation as an analysis tools. The distribution channel of Ang Thong's court doll can be separated into 3 channels which are direct distribution from the manufacturer, via the middleman and via the co-operated manufacturing group. In the direct distribution from the manufacturer channel, it was found that the manufacturer is given the highest rate of importance to how they keep the inventory. In the distribution via the middleman channel, it was found that the manufacturer is given the highest rate of importance to the distribution efficiency. But in the distribution via the co-operated manufacturing group, it was found that the manufacturer is given the highest rate of importance to the public relationship.

Keywords—Distribution, Court Doll, Ang Thong Province.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUNDS

ANG Thong province is located in the central part of Thailand. The distance from Bangkok, which is the capital city of Thailand is 105 kilometers by road transportation and 120 kilometers by water transportation. Ang Thong means "Golden Bowl" in Thai due to the agriculture and the rice field in the province. The neighboring provinces are Singburi province (Kai Bang Ra Chan District) in the North, Ayutthaya province (Bang Pa Hun District, Maharaj District, Pak Hai District and Tha Chang District) in the south and east and Suphanburi province (Meung District, Sri Prachan District, Derm Bang Nang Buach District) in the west.

The main mission of Ang Thong province is to improve and develop the competitiveness of the Ang Thong citizen and reduce the poverty in the province. As Ang Thong province is an agriculture province and the main income are from the agriculture product so there are lots of OTOP products which made from/by agriculture products. But the main problem of this province is the citizen is lacked of the marketing and distribution knowledge. So this article mainly aims to study the distribution of the OTOP product especially the court doll which is created by the wisdom of the ancestor.

In 1976, Her Royal Highness Queen Sirikit has paid a visit to the citizen of Bang Sadet District which was severely

suffered from the flood on that year and has an idea to create the local citizen a career by using the local ingredient, marl, to create the court doll.

This article is objected to study the pattern and the distribution of the court doll of Ang Thong province and to improve and develop the distribution efficiency of the court doll of Ang Thong province.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Supply Chain Management Definition

There are so many definition of supply chain management such as Supply chain management encompasses materials/supply management from the supply of basic raw materials to final product (and possible recycling and re-use). Supply chain management focuses on how firms utilize their suppliers' processes, technology and capability to enhance competitive advantage [1]. It is a management philosophy that extends traditional intra-enterprise activities by bringing trading partners together with the common goal of optimization and efficiency, Network of organizations that are involved, through upstream and downstream linkages, in the different processes and activities that produce value in the form of products and services in the hands of the ultimate consumer and etc [2]. But for the fresh vegetable supply chain definition there still have no specific definition for. This research is based on the supply chain definition not by the fresh vegetable supply chain definition.

B. Related Research

Reference [3] has concluded that the major problems of the community products are marketing channel and the public relation with their customers, lack of government support, transportation problem and packaging issue. So the researcher has suggest the new distribution channel which is via the post system or open the special kiosk in the department for the community product without the fee

Reference [4] found that logistics and supply chain management has a major effect to the OTOP business and also increase the competitiveness of the products. The better of the supply chain strategy will give the better change for the OTOP manufacturer to increase the sale and income.

Reference [5] and [6] noted that the significant factor for the customer to purchase the OTOP product is the quality of the product, price of the product and distribution channel aspect. So the manufacturer and the retailer should pay more attention to those aspects in order to increase the distribution channel and expand the market.

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III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is the descriptive research and exploration research which is objected to study the pattern and the distribution of the court doll of Ang Thong province and to improve and develop the distribution efficiency of the court doll of Ang Thong province in order to improve and develop the most suitable distribution and marketing pattern the court doll of Ang Thong province. In this research, the descriptive questionnaire is used. The population of this research is 50 local manufacturers of the court doll of Ang Thong province selected by using the purposive selection.

The questionnaire is developed by study the related information of the objective and literature review then created the drafted questionnaire and sent to the 2 veteran researchers for correction. After the correction had been done, the try-out drafted questionnaire is tested to verify the rightness of the questionnaire. The questionnaire can be divided in to 3 parts which are the general information of the local manufacturers, the information about the related process in the distribution of the court doll of Ang Thong province and the problem and difficulties of the process.

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is aim to study the distribution pattern and the significant factor of the distribution of Ang Thong Province's court doll in the distribution process. There are 3 processes which involved in the distribution which are the manufacturing process, distribution process and consuming process. And there are also 3 distribution patterns which are distribute by individual local, distribute by local Co-Op and distribution by the middleman. Fig. 1 is showed the whole conceptual framework of this article.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework of Distribution Pattern of Ang Thong's Province Court Doll

V. RESULT

A. Factors in the Distribution Process

There are several factors which has the significant to the distribution process but in this article only 6 main factors will be discussed which are goods handing, goods transportation, working efficiency, power of distribution, public relation and cost.

B. Distribute by Individual

In distribution by the local individual, the most significant factor of the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll is the goods handing which has the significant level at 4.32. The goods transportation also has the high significant level at 4.20. The result from the questionnaire show that the moderate significant factors are working efficiency and the cost which has a level at 3.42 and 3.52 respectively. And the factors which received the quite low significant level in the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll by local individual are power of distribution and public relation as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
THE SIGNIFICANT FACTOR OF THE DISTRIBUTION BY INDIVIDUAL IN ANG THONG PROVINCE'S COURT DOLL

Sourcing Process	Significant Level :Amount (Percentage)					\bar{X}	SD	Significant Level
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High			
1. Goods Handling	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	7 (14.00)	20 (40.00)	23 (46.00)	4.32	0.97	High
2. Goods Transportation	0 (0.00)	4 (8.00)	8 (16.00)	12 (24.00)	26 (52.00)	4.20	1.21	High
3. Working Efficiency	0 (0.00)	6 (12.00)	25 (25.00)	11 (22.00)	8 (16.00)	3.42	1.20	Moderate
4. Power of Distribution	3 (6.00)	25 (50.00)	18 (36.00)	3 (6.00)	1 (2.00)	2.08	1.09	Quite Low
5. Public Relation	15 (30.00)	15 (30.00)	11 (22.00)	9 (18.00)	0 (0.00)	2.28	0.96	Quite Low
6. Cost	0 (0.00)	10 (20.00)	8 (16.00)	28 (56.00)	4 (8.00)	3.52	0.93	Moderate

C. Distribution by CO-OP

In distribution by the local CO-OP, the most significant factor of the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll is the public relation which has the significant level at 4.70. The goods transportation and the power of distribution also have the high significant level at 4.56 and 4.54 respectively. The result from the questionnaire shows that the moderate significant factor is cost which has a level at 3.56. And the

factors which received the quite low significant level in the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll by local individual are goods handing and working efficiency.

D. Distribution via Middleman

In distribution via the middleman, the most significant factor of the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll is the power of distribution which has the significant level at

4.88. The public relation and the working efficiency also have the high significant level at 4.26 and 4.16 respectively. The result from the questionnaire shows that the moderate significant factor is cost which has a level at 3.40. And the

factor which received the quite low significant level in the distribution of Ang Thong province's court doll by local individual are goods handling and the transportation received a low significant at the 1.84.

TABLE II
THE SIGNIFICANT FACTOR OF THE DISTRIBUTION BY CO-OP IN ANG THONG PROVINCE'S COURT DOLL

Sourcing Process	Significant Level :Amount (Percentage)					\bar{X}	SD	Significant Level
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High			
1. Goods Handling	5 (10.00)	23 (46.00)	14 (28.00)	8 (16.00)	0 (0.00)	2.50	0.97	Quite Low
2. Goods Transportation	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	4 (8.00)	15 (30.00)	31 (62.00)	4.54	1.21	High
3. Working Efficiency	0 (0.00)	17 (34.00)	18 (36.00)	15 (30.00)	0 (0.00)	2.96	0.92	Quite Low
4. Power of Distribution	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (6.00)	16 (32.00)	31 (62.00)	4.56	1.09	High
5. Public Relation	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	15 (30.00)	35 (70.00)	4.70	0.66	High
6. Cost	0 (0.00)	8 (16.00)	16 (32.00)	16 (32.00)	10 (20.00)	3.56	0.96	Moderate

TABLE III
THE SIGNIFICANT FACTOR OF THE DISTRIBUTION VIA MIDDLEMAN IN ANG THONG PROVINCE'S COURT DOLL

Sourcing Process	Significant Level :Amount (Percentage)					\bar{X}	SD	Significant Level
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High			
1. Goods Handling	17 (34.00)	16 (32.00)	10 (20.00)	4 (8.00)	3 (6.00)	2.20	1.07	Quite Low
2. Goods Transportation	22 (44.00)	16 (32.00)	10 (20.00)	2 (4.00)	0 (0.00)	1.84	1.00	Low
3. Working Efficiency	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	9 (18.00)	24 (48.00)	17 (34.00)	4.16	0.93	High
4. Power of Distribution	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	6 (12.00)	44 (88.00)	4.88	0.60	High
5. Public Relation	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	2 (4.00)	33 (66.00)	15 (30.00)	4.26	0.84	High
6. Cost	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	34 (68.00)	12 (24.00)	4 (8.00)	3.40	1.17	Moderate

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the result of the research, as the distribution patterns can be divided into 3 solutions which are distribute by individual, distribute by the CO-OP and distribute by the middleman. The result can be concluded and given recommendation as below.

A. Distribute by Individual

In this type of distribution, the manufacturers will give the first priority on the goods handling process because this process is the only one that the manufacturers can manage by themselves. But the transportation process is also have a high significant as the court doll is a very fragile product as it was made from marl. If the damage to the goods is occurred, there is impossible to recover the condition of the goods.

And the reason why the public relation is the lowest significant factor is because the capability of the public relation or advertising of the manufacturer are low due to the education level of the manufacturer is normally only in grade 6. So the lacking of technology and knowledge is the main burden to this type of distribution.

B. Distribute by CO-OP

About the distribution by the CO-OP, the manufacturers are focused on the distribution power and the public relation the

most. But the transportation of the goods are very important as well, due to the goods are still belonging to the manufacturer so if the accident was occurred, the loss will be on the manufacturer and the CO-OP.

The significant which received the lowest significant is the efficiency of the working process. As the manufacturers are the same group of people who lives around so the villagers and the manufacturer will use the common way to work which might create the unprofessional workplace

C. Distribute by Middleman

In the distribution by the middleman, the most significant factor is the public relationship and the power of distribution. As the middleman always has a knowledge and wisdom about the marketing and distribution so the distribution will be more effective to the manufacturer. About the cost of the distribution is one of the last factors that the manufacturer will think about because as long as the middleman is taken place, the cost will be increased.

In the transportation process, the manufacturer will less concern with this process than in the other distribution. Due to once the goods was passed to the middleman; the manufacturers do not have to responsible to the goods even though the accident is occurred.

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